

APPROACHES OF SCHOLARS TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF LEXICAL DOUBLETS IN ENGLISH

G'afforova Nigora Abdunosirovna

nigoratehtaboyeva@gmail.com

Uzbek State world languages university

Scientific advisor: Doctor of Philological Sciences (DSc)

Professor Akhmedov O.S

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7976655>

Abstract: Any language has a social element, making it impossible for it to exist and grow apart from society. The primary goals of this work are to identify the fundamental components of the specificity of materials selection and adaptation in language teaching/learning and to define existing selected materials difficulties among various courses; to identify the advantages of selected materials in the classroom and adapting the materials; and to describe the structural and lexical-semantic domain of English doublets.

The formation of lexical doublets in English has been studied from a variety of perspectives by academics. The first one is the relational approach, which is primarily linked to paradigms that see lexical meaning as a web of interlinguistic relationships that influence one another. The structuralist paradigm, which was first proposed by Saussure and is one of the most well-known relational theories, calls for a dual view of the nature of lexical meaning. "The first is that meaning is realized as a relationship between the concept and the sound-image (the signifier and the signified), and that this relationship is reciprocal, with each evoking the other." This idea was later developed by Ullmann (1969) in his semantic triangle as one of the fundamental tenets of communication and as a representation of the realization of lexical meaning.

Next, the generativist school of thought and formalists in general use the symbolic approach to meaning-making in languages. Using explicit rules, symbols are used to manipulate meanings that are represented by them. The beliefs or thoughts that are related to one another through inferential relations make up the content of a sentence. That is to say, language is represented as a collection of symbols that the computation parses in accordance with a set of grammatical rules. The syntactic structures in the derivation are used by the computational system. Semantic characteristics are concentrated in the structure's nodes, where they eventually interact with fundamental motor and cognitive capacities. Although separate from the latter systems, the language faculty interacts with them, which makes inferencing easier.

The conceptual approach, the third method for modeling lexical doublets, incorporates all meanings—not just those that can be formalized—and is concerned with the psychological aspects of language comprehension as well as the depth of lexical knowledge. As metonymization, metaphorization, and constructionalization represent significant challenges for the structuralist and symbolic approach, this approach offers the tools for investigating concept formation based on spatial structures, meaning changes, and motivations for polysemies. (Croft and Cruse 2004, Paradis 2011, Traugott and Trousdale 2013).

The distributional approach, the fourth model approach for lexical doublets, is predicated on the idea that lexical meaning is dependent on the situations in which lexemes are used. The contextual representation of a word, which is defined as an abstraction over the linguistic

settings in which a word is encountered, can characterize at least some of its content (Miller and Charles 1991). When using distributional techniques, lexical items' semantic similarity is viewed as a function of the contexts in which they are employed, or more specifically, as a dependent variable of those contexts.

The representational theory of the mind is embraced by a very extensive family of theories, which see language as implicit system knowledge. According to this viewpoint, a theory of language attempts to model the information included in this knowledge using rules and principles. Thus, language is seen as a reality that exists exclusively within the mind, with precise psychological and neurological underpinnings; nevertheless, most modeling attempts focus on the structure of the information itself, rather than on the mental states of speakers. Thus, grammar examines information at an abstract level while modeling knowledge that is biophysically unsound in the brain according to Adger.

Lexical doublets are among the most well-established and complete lexico-semantic categories. Lexical doublets are said to be two or more frequently occurring words in the same language that have a history of being released from language dictionaries, sometimes as a result of re-appropriation included in their wealth, to pairs of words that are different from one another but have similar pronunciations. Etymological doublets are thought to be the most typical sort of lexical doublets. Russian linguists, Germanists, and general linguists use lexical doublets to Numerous scholars have extensively researched it in Turkology, such as W. W. Skeat (1882), O. F. Emerson (1915), R. Barber (R. The etymological analysis of terms in the English language first appeared in 1882, according to V. V. Skeat. The "Brief Etymological Dictionary" by Skit, which was released in the same year, is a scientific work that explores the history of word origins in the English language. In other words, it tells readers how and when a word came to be used in English from another language.

The works of A.G. Preobrazhensky (1959), M.O. Nikitina (1985), E.A. Zusmanovskaya (1998), M.P. Alekseeva (1988), V. G. Gak (2000), and others might be cited in relation to the study of lexical doublets in the Russian language. The topic of lexical doublets in the Uzbek language has been addressed at various levels by I. Kochkortoyev (1977), B. Daniyarov (2020), Sh. Rakhmatullayev (2006), A. Hojiyev (1981), R. Kongurov (1980), E. Begmatov (1985), M. Mirtojiyev (2010), and others. O. Yusupov (2020), an English and Uzbek author, studied doublets from a functional-semantic and linguocultural perspective. Azim Hajiyev's "Annotated Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" defines doublets as French.

The fact that it has the same semantics as the word "Doublet - double" - "double" and is derived from it highlights the fact that they are linguistic units with content. According to Sh. Rahmatullaev, lexical doublets are referred to as such if two lexemes (lexosememes) are identical in every way and lack a mutually identifying sign. It's a scientist. Absolute synonymy is another way of saying that a thing exists. The following is an explanation of doublets from the Uzbek language explanation dictionary. To double (to double) 1. One of two identical, equally valuable objects; the second of something. 2. Fake, imitation precious and rare stones. 3. It is a linguistic unit that can be used interchangeably with other words and has the exact same meaning.

The opposite terms "host" and "guest," which derive from the same PIE *ghóstis word and were already a doublet in Latin and later in Old French, are an example of how doublets can have contrasting meanings. Prior to the English borrowing. Additionally, doublets differ in the

degree of divergence of their shapes. For instance, it is simple to infer the relationship between levy and levee, but more difficult to infer the relationship between sovereign and soprano.

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